

National Security and the Right of Self-Defence: an Exposition of International Law and State Practice

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Abstract

The right of self-defence remains one of the most contested and vital principles in contemporary international law. This article offers a comprehensive overview of the legal framework governing the use of force in self-defence, examining both its theoretical foundations and practical application in state practice. The theoretical basis for the study is rooted in Realism Theory. The research methodology employed is qualitative. The study utilises both primary and secondary sources. By analysing the United Nations Charter, customary international law, and jurisprudence from the International Court of Justice, this article traces the evolution of the self-defence doctrine from its traditional conception to its modern challenges. It critically assesses the tensions between Article 51 of the UN Charter and customary international law, the principles of necessity and proportionality, the doctrine of anticipatory self-defence, and the contentious idea of pre-emptive action. Additionally, it examines state practice across various contexts, including armed attacks by non-state actors, cyber operations, and humanitarian issues. The article argues that although the legal framework imposes essential limits on the use of force, ambiguities in interpretation and inconsistent state practice pose significant challenges to international peace and security. Among other recommendations, it suggests that the international community should aim for greater clarity and consistency in defining and applying self-defence standards. The article concludes by addressing current debates, including the attribution problem in attacks by non-state actors, the sufficiency of existing law for cyber warfare, and the importance of multilateral cooperation in clarifying and strengthening the international legal regime governing self-defence.

Keywords: Self-defence, International law, Use of force, National security, Armed attack, Anticipatory self-defence, State practice

Introduction

The right of self-defence constitutes a fundamental principle of international law, representing both a natural right of states and a carefully regulated exception to the general prohibition on the use of force. Since the establishment of the United Nations in 1945, the legal framework governing self-defence has been shaped by the interplay between treaty law, customary international law, and evolving state practice. The tension between maintaining international

peace and security while respecting state sovereignty creates a complex legal landscape that continues to challenge international lawyers, policymakers, and courts (Brownlie, 1963; Dinstein, 2017). Before the twentieth century, international law imposed few restrictions on resorting to war. States had an essentially unlimited right to use force as a tool of national policy (Neff, 2005). However, customary international law gradually adopted a narrower view of self-defence as a legal justification for using force in response to armed attacks or imminent threats. The classic formulation came from the Caroline incident of 1837, where U.S. Secretary of State Daniel Webster outlined the fundamental test requiring that self-defence prove a necessity that is immediate, overwhelming, and leaves no room for choice of means or time for reflection, while also being proportionate.

Similarly, the Covenant of the League of Nations (1919) marked the first major multilateral attempt to limit the resort to war, followed by the Kellogg-Briand Pact (1928), which aimed to ban war as a tool of national policy. However, these instruments had notable gaps and lacked effective enforcement mechanisms. It was the United Nations Charter (1945) that established the modern legal framework, with Article 2(4) banning the use of force and Article 51 safeguarding the inherent right of individual or collective self-defence in response to an armed attack. This Charter framework underpins the modern understanding of state practice and legal doctrine.

According to Article 2(4) of the United Nations Charter, a general prohibition on the use of force is established, stating that all members shall refrain from the threat or use of force against the territorial integrity or political independence of any state. Article 51 explicitly preserves the inherent right of individual or collective self-defence in the event of an armed attack against a Member of the United Nations. The relationship between these two provisions has generated extensive scholarly debate and judicial interpretation—questions that have gained heightened significance in the 21st-century context of transnational terrorism, cyber warfare, and the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction. Despite the seemingly clear language of the UN Charter, the right of self-defence remains highly contested in both theory and practice. Several persistent and overlapping issues undermine the coherent application of this fundamental principle of international law.

First, there is a conflict between Article 51's clear requirement that an armed attack must happen before self-defence can be invoked and the customary international law doctrine of anticipatory self-defence, which allows states to respond to imminent threats. This tension between the Charter's explicit wording and customary law continues to result in different practices by states and in scholarly interpretations, creating legal uncertainty and unpredictability.

Second, the key issue of what defines an armed attack for the purposes of Article 51 remains debated. The International Court of Justice's distinction between uses of force and armed attacks in the Nicaragua case (1986) has been criticised for creating a dangerous gap in the law, in which states experiencing sub-threshold attacks lack adequate legal remedies under the Charter's self-defence framework.

Third, the rise of non-state actors, particularly international terrorist organisations, has fundamentally challenged the state-centric assumptions of the UN Charter framework. The question of whether and under what conditions attacks by non-state actors can trigger Article 51 self-defence rights, and the related problem of attribution, remains inadequately resolved in both law and practice.

Fourth, the rise of cyber operations as a means of interstate competition and conflict has revealed substantial gaps in the current legal framework. Traditional concepts developed for kinetic force do not easily adapt to cyber operations, leaving unresolved questions about thresholds, attribution, and proportionate responses in the cyber domain.

Fifth, inconsistent and opportunistic uses of self-defence by states have compromised the legitimacy and coherence of the legal framework. States have invoked self-defence in situations such as the 2003 invasion of Iraq, which received little international legal support, fostering perceptions that powerful states apply the law selectively to serve strategic interests rather than as a genuine legal constraint. These issues collectively threaten the stability of the international legal order and the Charter's core commitment to preventing war.

Against this backdrop, this work aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the legal framework governing the use of force in self-defence, exploring both its theoretical foundations and practical application in state practice. It examines the United Nations Charter, customary international law, and jurisprudence of the International Court of Justice.

Conceptual Review

National security

National Security has been defined by various scholars, yet despite the wealth of literature, there is no universal definition. Udeh and Nwokerobia (2021) define national security as the policies and practices adopted by a state to protect its sovereignty, territorial integrity, political institutions, economic systems, and the safety and well-being of its citizens against both internal and external threats. The scholars also added that it involves not only traditional military protection but also a broader scope, which includes political stability, economic resilience, social cohesion, and the capacity to address transnational threats such as terrorism, organised crime, cyber threats, and pandemics.

Accordingly, Ekwutosi, Effiong and Inyang (2021) defined national security as the systematic effort by a state to ensure that its sovereignty, political independence, and the safety of its citizens, institutions, and values are not threatened by internal or external forces. These include protection against military aggression, political instability, espionage, and subversive activities that could weaken the state's authority and governance.

This study views national security as extending beyond borders to include protecting human security, social stability, and the overall well-being of the population. It also encompasses strategic actions to address threats such as terrorism, organised crime, pandemics, and

environmental issues, recognising that the security and development of citizens are closely connected to the security of the state.

Self Defence

The scholarship on self-defence in international law is extensive and highlights the enduring importance of the subject. Foundational works have established the theoretical and doctrinal boundaries within which contemporary debates take place. Brownlie's (1963) 'International Law and the Use of Force by States' remains the key restrictive account of self-defence, arguing that the UN Charter largely replaced customary law and that Article 51 allows self-defence only in response to actual armed attacks. Brownlie's textual and historical analysis has significantly influenced strict interpretations of the armed attack threshold. Bowett (1958) provided an early permissive counter-argument, asserting that Article 51's reference to an inherent right maintains customary law and permits anticipatory self-defence, a view that continues to influence contemporary discussions. Dinstein's (2017) *War, Aggression and Self-Defence*, now in its sixth edition, offers the most comprehensive systematic treatment of the law governing self-defence. The scholar also reveals and develops a detailed analytical framework for understanding armed attacks, necessity, proportionality, and collective self-defence. Neff (2005) provides essential historical perspective through his analysis of the development of laws governing war from antiquity to the modern era, placing contemporary self-defence doctrine within a longer historical context.

Also, Franck (2002) examines the conditions under which force may legitimately be used, arguing that both legality and legitimacy are necessary criteria for evaluating uses of force. Goodrich et al. (1969) provide authoritative commentary on the UN Charter's drafting history and textual provisions, offering invaluable context for understanding the scope and purpose of Article 51. Gray's (2018) fourth edition of *International Law and the Use of Force* provides the most current comprehensive survey of state practice regarding the use of force, incorporating developments through the Syrian conflict and beyond. Alexandrov (1996) provides a systematic analysis of self-defence practice, with particular focus on anticipatory self-defence cases. Franck (2002) and Gray (2008) both examine the controversial U.S. National Security Strategy's pre-emption doctrine, finding it inconsistent with Charter requirements. Byers (2003) criticises pre-emptive self-defence from both legal and political philosophy perspectives, arguing that it represents an attempt by hegemonic states to alter legal rules to serve their strategic interests.

Tams (2009) examines the expanding practice of using force against terrorist organisations, concluding that post-9/11 developments have altered some traditional rules while leaving others unchanged. Deeks (2012) develops a normative framework for extraterritorial self-defence, analysing the 'unwilling or unable' doctrine's legal foundations and suitable constraints. Roscini (2014) offers a comprehensive analysis of how existing international law applies to cyber operations, including the dimensions of the use of force and self-defence. Schmitt's (2013) Tallinn Manual stands as the most authoritative expert analysis of international law relevant to cyber warfare.

Furthermore, Green (2009) examines the International Court of Justice's jurisprudence on self-defence across multiple cases, identifying a consistent pattern of restrictive interpretation that emphasises the importance of the armed attack threshold and the necessity and proportionality criteria. Ruys (2010) systematically investigates the development of the armed attack concept within both customary law and state practice, tracing its evolution through key cases such as Nicaragua, Oil Platforms, and Armed Activities. Corten (2010) offers a comprehensive analysis of the prohibition on the use of force, including a detailed review of self-defence claims and their connection to broader Charter norms.

Theoretical Framework

This article is primarily guided by a legalist-institutionalist theoretical framework, complemented by insights from constructivism. Legalism, as Judith Shklar (1964) described it, is the ethical stance that considers moral conduct a matter of rules. In international relations, this means that international law forms a genuine normative system to which states are committed, and by which their actions can be assessed. From this viewpoint, the UN Charter's framework for the use of force is not merely an expression of political power but a binding legal regime that restricts state behaviour and has normative significance beyond enforcement.

Liberal institutionalism, associated with scholars such as Keohane (1984) and Ikenberry (2001), offers a complementary framework. It holds that international institutions, including the United Nations and the broader international legal order, mitigate the worst tendencies of international anarchy by fostering cooperation, reducing uncertainty, and establishing shared norms. According to this view, the prohibition on the use of force and the right to self-defence serve as essential elements of a managed international order, which states have strong interests in maintaining, even when they occasionally breach its rules. This framework explains both why states continue to invoke legal justifications for their military actions—because legitimacy entails real costs and benefits—and why the erosion of those justifications through expansive self-defence claims becomes a significant institutional concern.

Constructivism and the Role of Norms

Constructivism, associated particularly with Wendt (1999) and Finnemore and Sikkink (1998), adds an important dimension by emphasising the role of norms, identities, and discourse in shaping state behaviour. A constructivist perspective shows that states do not merely comply with or violate international law; they also engage with it discursively, seeking to influence its meaning through their justifications, patterns of practice, and 'opinio juris'. From this viewpoint, the increase in self-defence claims is not just a sign of norm violation but an active effort to redefine the norm itself. Whether such efforts succeed depends on the extent to which other states and institutions accept or reject these new interpretations.

Relevance of the Framework

Together, these theoretical perspectives enable this article to explore not only whether specific self-defence claims are legally valid but also why states make them, how they are received, and

what impact patterns of claim-making have on the normative structure of international law. The framework is suitable for a study at the intersection of law and politics because it considers both seriously: it neither reduces international law to a mere tool of power politics nor treats it as entirely autonomous from the political context in which it operates.

Methodology

This article employs a doctrinal legal research methodology combined with a comparative analysis of state practice. Doctrinal analysis involves a systematic examination and interpretation of primary legal sources, including treaty texts, judicial decisions, and authoritative commentaries, to clarify and explain the current state of the law. Primary sources examined include the text of the United Nations Charter, particularly Articles 2(4) and 51; relevant Security Council and General Assembly resolutions; judgments and advisory opinions of the International Court of Justice, such as the Nicaragua case (1986), Oil Platforms (2003), Armed Activities on the Territory of the Congo (2005), and the Advisory Opinion on Nuclear Weapons (1996); and correspondence and formal legal positions submitted by states to international bodies. Secondary sources, including academic treatises, journal articles, and expert commentaries such as the Tallinn Manual, support the analysis by offering interpretive frameworks and synthesising patterns in primary sources. The article adopts a comparative approach to analyse patterns of state practice across various jurisdictions and contexts. Cases examined include Israel's 1967 and 1981 military operations, the United States' responses to the September 11, 2001 attacks and the 2003 Iraq invasion, NATO's Article 5 invocation, and operations against ISIL/Da'esh.

Empirical Analysis of National Security and the Right of Self-Defence:

Armed Attack Threshold and the Nicaragua Standard

The International Court of Justice's Nicaragua decision (1986) established that Article 51 requires distinguishing between armed attacks and lesser uses of force. The Court held that not every prohibited use of force qualifies as an armed attack justifying self-defence. This distinction, while doctrinally coherent, creates a gap in legal remedies: states subjected to low-level force or covert support for armed groups may face prohibited uses of force without clear authority to respond in kind. Subsequent decisions in Oil Platforms (2003) and Armed Activities (2005) reinforced this threshold requirement, adding a component on scale and effects.

Necessity, Proportionality, and Immediacy

The principles of necessity, proportionality, and immediacy establish core substantive limits on self-defence. Necessity entails that peaceful alternatives are unavailable and that the defensive action targets the source of the attack. Proportionality does not require exact mathematical equivalence but mandates that defensive measures be appropriate to the level of threat, forbidding actions aimed at overthrowing the attacking government or claiming territory. Immediacy distinguishes true defence from unlawful retaliation, although the doctrine of accumulated events indicates that a strict temporal requirement may not accurately reflect the realities of prolonged asymmetric conflicts.

Anticipatory Self-Defence in Practice

Practice shows that an outright ban on anticipatory self-defence has little support. Israel's 1967 attack on Egyptian airfields was widely accepted, despite technically pre-empting an expected attack. However, Israel's 1981 Osirak strike on Iraq's nuclear reactor was condemned by the Security Council, illustrating that action against future non-imminent threats is not recognised as lawful anticipatory self-defence. The Bush Doctrine's concept of pre-emptive self-defence, as applied in Iraq (2003), received little international legal backing and remains largely rejected. The prevailing consensus is limited: anticipatory self-defence against genuinely imminent threats that meet the Caroline criteria is allowed; pre-emptive action against non-imminent threats is not.

Non-State Actors: Post-9/11 Developments

The international community's response to the September 11 attacks marked a significant development in self-defence law. Security Council Resolutions 1368 and 1373 acknowledged the United States' inherent right to self-defence, and NATO's invocation of Article 5 confirmed that attacks by non-state actors can constitute armed attacks. However, the conditions under which states may use force in third-state territories against non-state actors remain debated. The 'unwilling or unable' doctrine has gained traction in state practice but has not been formally endorsed by the International Court of Justice, resulting in ongoing legal uncertainty.

Attribution Challenges

The ICJ's effective control standard for attribution, established in Nicaragua and reaffirmed in the Genocide case (2007), sets a high evidentiary bar for proving that attacks by non-state actors can be attributed to a state. States supporting terrorist organisations often do so in ways that fall short of having effective control over specific operations, allowing them to maintain plausible deniability while providing substantial material and organisational support. This gap between actual involvement and legal attribution has important practical implications for self-defence claims.

Cyber Operations: An Emerging Frontier

Cyber operations pose the most significant emerging challenge to self-defence law. The Tallinn Manual's conclusions that cyber operations can constitute uses of force and armed attacks based on their scale and effects provide an important normative contribution, but they remain non-binding expert assessments. The technical difficulties of attribution, the risk of misattribution, and the lack of clear treaty rules create considerable uncertainty. State practice is still developing, with no clear examples of states successfully asserting Article 51 rights in response to cyber-attacks, although the United States and NATO have indicated that severe cyber-attacks could provoke self-defence responses.

Similarities between the Charter Framework and Customary International Law on Self-Defence

Although their legal origins and historical backgrounds differ, the UN Charter's self-defence framework and pre-Charter customary international law share important substantive similarities

that reflect enduring principles of international order. Both frameworks recognise self-defence as an inherent right of states. The Caroline doctrine's core assertion of self-defence as a legal entitlement was explicitly carried into Article 51's reference to the 'inherent right' of self-defence. Both traditions base the right on the vital necessity of state survival and sovereignty, acknowledging that no legal system can sensibly demand states to passively accept armed destruction.

Necessity and proportionality are fundamental requirements for both regimes. The Caroline formula explicitly states that self-defensive action must be necessary, leaving no room for choice of means or deliberation, and must be proportionate, avoiding anything unreasonable or excessive beyond what is essential for self-defence. Article 51 incorporates these principles, which the ICJ has consistently highlighted as key limitations on self-defence under both treaty and customary law.

Both frameworks regard self-defence as a special justification for the use of force rather than a broad authorisation. In the pre-Charter period, the general right to wage war was limited by the Caroline exception for defensive necessity. Under the Charter, the general ban on force in Article 2(4) is subject to the Article 51 exception for self-defence against armed attack. In both scenarios, restraint is the default stance, with self-defence representing a narrowly justified deviation from that baseline.

Both frameworks have been developed through practice-driven evolution by states, with legal content significantly influenced by how states have actually behaved and justified their actions. The Caroline doctrine itself originated from diplomatic correspondence, not judicial decisions or treaty language. Likewise, the application of Article 51 to non-state actors and anticipatory scenarios has been largely shaped by state practice following major security events, especially the September 11 attacks.

Differences between the Charter Framework and Customary International Law on Self-Defence

Despite these similarities, the UN Charter framework brought about significant changes from the pre-Charter customary law of self-defence, creating important points of divergence that still influence legal debates.

The most notable difference relates to the triggering condition for self-defence. Under pre-Charter customary law, self-defence could be invoked in response to imminent threats, as demonstrated by the Caroline formula: the need for defensive action could arise before an attack actually began. Article 51's wording requires an armed attack to have occurred, which restrictive scholars have interpreted as imposing a higher threshold, demanding proof of actual hostilities before self-defence is considered lawful.

The Charter framework established a collective security mechanism that is completely absent from pre-Charter customary law. Article 51 explicitly states that self-defence may only continue until the Security Council has taken necessary measures to uphold peace and security, and it

requires reporting. These provisions place self-defence within an institutional structure intended to restrict unilateral use of force and to direct security decisions through multilateral means. Pre-Charter customary law did not acknowledge any comparable institutional restriction.

The Charter framework has introduced a much higher level of formalisation and legalisation of self-defence claims. While the Caroline doctrine was outlined in diplomatic correspondence and developed through state practice, Article 51 is a binding treaty provision subject to interpretation by the International Court of Justice. This institutional support has created a substantial body of judicial precedent that influences self-defence law in ways that pre-Charter customary law never did.

The threshold of violence needed to invoke self-defence rights varies between the two frameworks. Pre-Charter customary law recognised self-defence against a wider range of threats, including insults to national honour and other acts that would now be considered insufficient for armed attack. The Charter framework, as interpreted by the ICJ in Nicaragua and subsequent cases, requires attacks of a certain scale and seriousness before self-defence is lawful, explicitly excluding minor border incidents and low-level uses of force from the armed attack category.

The prohibition on force in Article 2(4) has no clear equivalent in pre-Charter customary international law. While the Kellogg-Briand Pact purported to outlaw war, it lacked enforcement mechanisms and permitted broad exceptions. The Charter's prohibition, supported by the Security Council's enforcement authority, creates a fundamentally different normative environment in which self-defence functions as an exception to a strong overall rule rather than as one of many competing state rights.

Lessons to Learn from the Comparative Analysis of International Self-Defence Frameworks

The comparative analysis of the Charter framework and customary international law on self-defence, along with the review of diverse state practice across different contexts, provides several important lessons for understanding and developing international law on the use of force.

First, legal texts alone are insufficient to determine the content of self-defence law. Both the Caroline formula and Article 51 have been significantly elaborated, modified, and contested through state practice and judicial interpretation. Legal scholars and practitioners must pay close attention to the accumulation of precedents, diplomatic positions, and institutional responses that provide concrete content to general legal standards. Focusing solely on treaty text risks overlooking the dynamic evolution of legal norms.

Secondly, effective legal constraints depend on institutional backing and consistent enforcement. The experience of the League of Nations Covenant, the Kellogg-Briand Pact, and the UN Charter shows that legal bans on force are effective only when supported by credible institutional mechanisms. The Security Council's frequent inability to act due to disagreements among major powers has consistently weakened the Charter's collective security framework and heightened reliance on the self-defence doctrine to address gaps caused by institutional failures.

Third, clarity in legal rules serves multiple functions beyond merely constraining states. Clear legal standards enable states to coordinate expectations, reduce misperceptions and miscalculations, and establish accountability for violations. The persistent ambiguity surrounding anticipatory self-defence has allowed states to invoke the concept opportunistically while depriving it of the legal legitimacy that clearer standards would provide. The international community should pursue greater clarification of these rules through authoritative processes.

Fourth, the law must adapt to genuinely new security threats while maintaining core principles. The rise of non-state actor threats and cyber operations introduces qualitatively new challenges that the Charter's drafters could not have foreseen. The comparative analysis shows that customary international law can evolve in response to changing circumstances, as demonstrated by post-9/11 developments concerning non-state actors. However, such evolution must be guided by principled reasoning rather than the strategic interests of powerful states.

Fifth, proportionality and multilateral accountability are the strongest constraints on abuse of self-defence. Throughout different legal frameworks and historical periods, requirements for proportionality and some form of multilateral accountability have consistently served as the most effective practical limits on excessive self-defence claims. Enhancing these requirements through more rigorous Security Council oversight, increased transparency in self-defence justifications, and the consistent application of proportionality by the ICJ offers the most promising path towards a more stable and legitimate legal framework.

Conclusion

The right of self-defence holds a central yet contested role in modern international law. While the foundational principles established by the UN Charter remain intact, their application to contemporary security issues sparks considerable debate and inconsistent state practices. This article reveals both lasting principles and ongoing ambiguities in self-defence law. The core requirements of armed attack, necessity, proportionality, and immediacy serve as key limits on the use of force, embodying international law's dual aims of safeguarding state sovereignty and maintaining global peace. The International Court of Justice has reaffirmed these principles through consistent jurisprudence, highlighting a strict interpretation of self-defence exceptions to the general ban on force. This jurisprudence plays a crucial role in restricting unilateral force and ensuring stability in international relations. Nonetheless, substantial challenges remain. The armed attack threshold leaves gaps where force may breach Article 2(4) without activating Article 51 self-defence rights. The debate over anticipatory self-defence persists despite decades of discussion. Attacks by non-state actors and cyber operations add further complexities that the current framework struggles to address. The standard for attribution based on effective control may be too strict to cover modern forms of state support for terrorism, while alternative approaches risk removing meaningful limits on cross-border force.

The comparative analysis of the Charter framework and customary international law yields important lessons: legal texts need institutional support to be effective; clarity in legal rules serves vital functions; law must evolve while maintaining core principles; and proportionality

with multilateral accountability offers the strongest restraint on self-defence abuse. These lessons should guide efforts to clarify and strengthen the international legal regime governing self-defence in the coming decades. The right of self-defence will continue to develop through state practice, judicial decisions, and scholarly analysis. However, its development must be guided by a commitment to the Charter's vision of an international order governed by law rather than force. Only through such dedication can the international community realise the Charter's goal of protecting future generations from the scourge of war while respecting states' legitimate rights to defend themselves against genuine threats.

Recommendations

Based on the preceding analysis, several recommendations arise for improving the international legal framework governing self-defence.

First, the international community should work towards greater clarity and consistency in articulating and applying standards for self-defence. While the International Court of Justice has provided important guidance, states must show greater commitment to consistently applying legal principles instead of opportunistically invoking self-defence to justify desired actions. The Security Council should establish more systematic processes for reviewing self-defence claims against agreed legal criteria.

Second, states and international institutions should establish clearer frameworks for addressing threats from non-state actors while maintaining essential Charter constraints. The unwilling or unable doctrine, when properly limited by genuine evidentiary standards and necessity requirements, could offer a practical approach to extraterritorial self-defence against non-state actors. Nevertheless, its acceptance depends on multilateral agreement on specific criteria—including the type of evidence needed to prove unwillingness or inability—to prevent misuse.

Third, the international community must address cyber operations by clarifying existing legal principles and possibly creating new norms or agreements specific to the cyber context. The Tallinn Manual process offers a useful model for experts to engage with these issues, but states need to turn such expert work into practical and binding commitments. An international convention or agreed principles on cyber operations and the use of force would greatly reduce legal uncertainty.

Fourth, states should improve transparency regarding self-defence claims through more detailed and timely reporting to the Security Council. Comprehensive reporting practices would aid Security Council oversight, allow other states to assess claims, and help develop clearer norms through accumulated precedents. The reporting requirement of Article 51 should be regarded as a substantive obligation rather than merely a procedural formality.

Fifth, the Security Council should more effectively exercise its Chapter VII responsibilities. Article 51 considers self-defence as a temporary measure until Security Council action can be taken, yet the Council's frequent paralysis has essentially made self-defence the main response to security threats. Reforms that enable more consistent Council action—including voluntary

restraint of veto use in cases involving mass atrocities and serious threats to peace—would lessen the reliance on self-defence doctrine to counter all security challenges.

Finally, scholars and practitioners must focus on the Charter's core aims: preventing war, safeguarding sovereignty, and maintaining international peace and security. These aims should inform the interpretation of vague provisions and the evaluation of new practices. While law must evolve with changing realities, such changes should reinforce rather than weaken the essential Charter framework for collective security.

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